

Rice-based cropping systems

Yield of 10 mungbean cultivars evaluated in intensive ricebased cropping systems

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One serious constraint to expanding mungbean production in the tropics is time. Most cultivars require more than a month for flowering and pod setting. Sequential cluster maturation necessitates frequent hand harvesting. This study was undertaken to select an early-maturing mungbean with high yield potential for inclusion in intensive rice-based cropping systems.

Ten mungbean cultivars were evaluated under eight growing conditions at IRRI in 1978-80. Yield at harvest (first priming at 60-65 days after sowing [DS], second at 70-75 DS, and third at 85-90 DS) for each growing condition was used to calculate a mean maturity index:

$$\frac{\sum (\text{days from planting to each harvest}) \times (\text{yield at each harvest})}{\text{total yield}}$$

Cultivars differed considerably in yield at harvest (see figure).

Based on daily production and mean maturity indices, CES IT-2, CESU-I, S8 (Green), CES IF-5, and CES 14 were late maturing and had relatively low yields. Among them CES IT-2 and S8 (Green) are characterized by long reproductive flushes, indicating that a considerable proportion of harvest can be expected at third priming. In areas where agriculture is not so intensive and moisture is not limiting, these cultivars may be grown successfully.

Cultivars high-yielding on a daily basis were MG 50-10A(Y), CES ID-21, M350, and EG Mg 174-3, producing about 90% of total yield at 60-70 DS.

About 95% of the total production of CES 55, M350, and MG 50-10A(Y) was harvested from the first and second primings. This indicates that these cultivars are early-maturing (lowest mean

Proportions of total yield harvested at 3 different dates (mean of 8 trials) for 10 mungbean cultivars. IRRI, 1978-80. DS = days after sowing. The figure above each bar indicates daily production (kg/ha).

maturity index), with flowering occurring mostly in two reproductive flushes.

This study suggests that cultivar MG 50-10A(Y), with the highest daily production and lowest mean maturity index, can be grown in parts of the humid tropics where cropping intensity is very high and limited time exists for growing a third crop between or after two rice crops. ■

Agronomic evaluation of farmers' dryland monoculture and mixed-cropping practices in Bangladesh

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Bangladeshi farmers practice extensive mixed cropping of dryland cereals — wheat, barley, and Italian millet *Setaria italica* — and pulses and oilseeds — chickpea, lentil, mustard, linseed, and grasspea *Lathyrus sarivus* — in the dry winter or rabi (Oct to Mar). Mixed cropping provides opportunities for increased and diversified agricultural production from limited land. It is a form of risk aversion through crop intensification. It makes efficient use of available soil moisture, suppresses weed growth, and improves soil fertility

through the use of legumes.

But productivity of current mixed-cropping practices is generally low. There is considerable scope for improvement, particularly in plant population regulation, conservation of residual soil moisture, crop configuration, planting schedule, and crop establishment.

In the 1979-80 rabi, yields of crops in solid and mixed stands were assessed

Av yield of farmers' dryland wheat, barley, and chickpea in monoculture and mixed cropping with residual soil moisture on two land types. BRRI dryland cropping systems research site, Alimganj, Rajshahi district, Bangladesh, 1979-80 dry season.

Land type	Crop species	Sample fields		Yield (t/ha)
		No	%	
Upland	Wheat	6	11	0.93
	Barley	27	50	1.03
	Chickpea	10	19	0.83
	Barley + chickpea	11	20	0.70 + 0.75
Lowland	Wheat	1	2.7	2.21
	Wheat + chickpea	8	21.6	1.11 + 0.74
	Barley + chickpea	28	75.7	0.82 + 1.05

through crop-cut studies in two adjacent blocks of upland and lowland fields in a dryland farming area (total annual rainfall about 1,438 mm, with 3-4 months wet and more than 6 months dry) on the Ganges river bank in Bangladesh. On both land types rabi crops were preceded by either one or two rainfed rice crops. Visual observation indicated higher soil moisture in the lowland fields than in the upland fields. ■